

Features Of The Development Of Professional Psychology In Future Engineers

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Abstract: *The article discusses the relevance and need for enhanced psychological training of engineering personnel. This is due to the fact that today the success of their professional activities depends not only on solving purely production problems, but also on taking into account the psychological factor in building joint activities.*

Keywords — engineer, professional education of engineers, psychological training of engineers.

INTRODUCTION

The current level of development and the nature of social production, associated with the transition of the national economy to market principles and the desire to integrate into the world economy, indicates the need for significant transformations in this area, the successful organization of which can be carried out, in our opinion, only with highly professional staffing, meeting the requirements of the global educational space.

In our opinion, one of the effective ways to solve emerging problems in engineering education is enhanced psychological training of personnel. It is she who must ensure the preparation of engineers “for life in a democratic society, to instill responsibility for their choices, their actions, their activities and their consequences, to form psychological readiness for successful work in a market economy, to reduce the destructive interaction of young people with their social environment” [1, p.56].

The training of a modern engineer should be based not only on the fact that he must “have a good knowledge of engineering and production technology, be able to successfully carry out engineering tasks, but first of all look for answers to the following questions: in what place is it more effective to use a particular employee, how to create more comfortable working conditions, using an individual approach, etc.” [2, p. 134].

The need for psychological training of modern engineers, in our opinion, is due to the fact that: the increasing role of the human factor in the conditions of democratization of society and the establishment of market relations determine the effectiveness of management only on the basis of taking into account the individual characteristics of each person [3, p. 17]. And the skills of understanding, revealing and activating these features can only be formed in the process of psychological preparation; changing the nature and goals of social production and its orientation toward the individual requires the humanization of all professional training, part of which is psychological knowledge; The specialist spends a significant part of his working time on various types of management communication. Therefore, mastering the culture and knowledge of the laws of the psychology of interpersonal communication becomes an integral and important element in

the formation of an engineer; The effectiveness of joint activities of large groups of people is mainly determined by the psychological climate in the team and the psychological “comfort” of each person. A favorable environment conducive to achieving the strategic goals of the organization and creating the most comfortable conditions for each individual can only be created by a specialist with special psychological training; in modern conditions, each specialist in the process of professional activity constantly has to perform a significant amount of work associated with great physical and emotional-psychological stress. In this regard, in the learning process there is a need to form and develop students’ emotional-volitional sphere and resilience to stressful situations; It is important for every specialist to be aware of his abilities, capabilities and limitations, to reveal his internal psychological reserves in order to set the highest possible goals for himself and successfully organize the joint work of large groups of people to achieve them [4, p. 344].

To do this, he needs to know the methods and means of self-improvement and self-actualization that psychology can equip him with; An analysis of the activities of engineers indicates that it is associated with the need to train and educate the people with whom he works and, as statistics show, they spend most of their time organizing and conducting them. This circumstance determines that professional activity contains a certain set of pedagogical functions; It is also necessary to take into account that an important social function of a specialist is also creating a family and raising children. It also requires appropriate psychological knowledge.

The goals, content and structure of psychological training imply the formation in future engineers of the necessary amount of psychological knowledge, skills and abilities, not only as an element of general culture, but also as the most important toolkit for performing production and management functions. Psychological training gives the future specialist a holistic understanding of the system of psychological knowledge and instills skills in navigating it, showing its importance in future activities and, accordingly, in professional training. Today, more and more people are aware of the need for psychological knowledge.

Psychology is gradually transforming from a science that provides purely academic knowledge into scientific and practical disciplines that are vitally important and necessary for all people. It seems that we should not look for current and

irrelevant problems in these sciences. They simply cannot contain irrelevant problems, since they are about a person, his life and activities. Psychological knowledge is needed in all spheres of public life, wherever people live and work. In any of them, you need to know the psychology of people, take it into account and develop it in accordance with the needs of society. Engineers especially need this knowledge in the process of their professional activities [5, pp. 5-6].

In professional activities, people are fully included in the structure of the organization, the system of communication connections and the diverse technological and socio-psychological processes occurring in it. And for the most efficient operation of production, it is necessary that each employee is included in the system of power relations, integrated into the team, is loyal to cultural norms and accepts existing and generally accepted core values. These provisions are considered in psychology and, to a greater extent, are studied by the psychology of management, the focus of which is "the study and improvement of pedagogical and psychological mechanisms of systematic, based on reliable knowledge, interaction of the subject of management with the object in order to preserve its qualitative specificity and integrity, normal functioning and successful movement towards a given goal" [6, p. 367].

Pedagogical features of the development of professional qualities of future engineers should have the following qualities:

Communication skills. Competent speech, tact, a sense of humor, and easy communication skills are the characteristics of a sociable person. They will help you find a common language with clients, colleagues and management. Sociable people find it easy to organize their work and, if necessary, the work of their team. For sales managers, actors and journalists, communication skills are one of the main qualities.

Determination. An employee works much more productively if he knows how to set and achieve goals, complete complex tasks and manage time wisely. This also includes courage, the ability to independently make difficult decisions without overstepping the boundaries of one's powers.

Responsibility. A responsible person earns the trust not only of the employer, but also of the people who surround him in everyday life. When tasks are completed efficiently and on time, the team's work goes on as usual.

Learning ability. The ability and desire of an employee to acquire knowledge and master useful skills are important today in any field of activity. It is easier to improve an employee's qualifications than to open a new vacancy. Self-improvement is a chance for advancement.

Stress resistance. Work is often associated with stress, failure and conflict. A distinctive feature of a high-class specialist is overcoming difficult situations without loss of productivity. Emotional stability negates future moments of crisis.

Determine a successful combination of professional qualities and start improving them now.

The conclusions that a specialist will make based on an in-depth study of the employee's personality are necessary for the implementation of his pedagogical influences. They can be of great importance both in developing the content of training (it can vary depending on the conditions and circumstances), in selecting the style of education (authoritarian or democratic), in choosing the type and frequency of control, and in creating the necessary conditions for the implementation of educational or educational process.

So, the psychological readiness of an engineer is associated with the ability to implement the following goals and objectives:

- evaluate personnel;
- to form knowledge, skills and abilities;
- provide individual assistance;
- be able to effectively apply instructive and motivating measures;
- be able to organize a favorable educational and learning environment;
- create a favorable moral and psychological climate for highly productive work of people.

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